

**IMPROVEMENT OF CULTURAL AWARENESS BY MEANS OF TEACHING
FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES**

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Abstract. *The article emphasizes the noteworthiness of social mindfulness headway in the midst of inaccessible tongue considers almost. The paper reveals the concepts of culture and linguaculture. It illustrates that cross-cultural competence contributes and plans a understudy to profitable life in a multicultural world. A couple of models of the learning get ready are shown.*

Keywords: *language teaching; cross-cultural communication; cultural self-identification; cultural awareness; cross-cultural competence; linguaculture; cognitive space.*

Аннотация. *В статье подчеркивается значимость прогресса социальной осознанности среди недоступных языку мыслей почти. В статье раскрываются понятия культуры и лингвокультуры. Это демонстрирует, что кросс-культурная компетентность способствует и планирует дублера к продуктивному жизнь в мультикультурном мире. Представлено несколько моделей подготовки к обучению.*

Ключевые слова: *обучение языку; межкультурное общение; культурная самоидентификация; культурная осведомленность; межкультурная компетентность; лингвокультура; познавательное пространство*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada uzoq dialektal aks ettirish kontekstida ijtimoiy ongni rivojlantirish muhimligi ta'kidlangan. Maqolada madaniyat va til madaniyati tushunchalari ochib berilgan. Bu madaniyatlararo kompetensiya ko'p madaniyatli dunyoda samarali hayotni o'rganishga yordam berishini va rejalashtirishini ko'rsatadi. Treningga tayyorgarlikning bir nechta modellari keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *til o'rgatish; madaniyatlararo muloqot; madaniy o'ziga xoslik; madaniy xabardorlik; madaniyatlararo kompetensiya; til madaniyati; ta'lim maydoni.*

Without a doubt, it can be contended that intercultural communication is an imperative zone within the cutting edge multicultural world. Nowadays we are seeing exceptional human portability. There are 1 billion individuals on the move out of the 7 billion individuals on the planet. These are various sightseers, members in trade gatherings, logical conferences and political missions, business visionaries, understudies, contracted laborers, driving masters, temporary workers, inside uprooted people, outcasts, vagrants. The list can be proceeded uncertainly. English as the dialect of intercultural communication is called upon nowadays to join together these bunches of individuals. Nowadays, language specialists are bringing intercultural competence to the fore. Intercultural competence may be a position in dialect instructing and learning that emphasizes the interdependency of dialect and culture and the significance of intercultural understanding as the objective of dialect instruction. It is this competence that permits and contributes to the readiness of understudies for life in a multicultural world.

The significance of creating intercultural communicative competence along side phonetic competence is the result of the advanced necessities of the students themselves in procuring

intercultural aptitudes for intercultural communication, within the handle of which they can see the etymological and social boundary. Intercultural competence preparing incorporates the improvement of a buyer of instructive administrations with a basic social mindfulness, social viewpoint and behavior, as well as skills and states of mind to get it and successfully interact with individuals from other societies, that's , to become a full-fledged member within the intercultural field, whereas remaining phonetically proficient. Nowadays, there's a got to move from the conventional position of instructing a outside dialect to a social one in arrange to create the dialect and intercultural competencies of understudies. Culture could be a exceptionally complex wonder, a complex framework of concepts, demeanors, values, convictions, traditions, behaviors, hones and customs. It is the way of life of the individuals who make up the social gather, as well as the artifacts they deliver, the teach they make. Dialect and culture are inseparably connected. Dialect and culture are not isolated units, they are comprehended at the same time, supporting and creating each other

Fig.1. Teaching and Learning for the development of cultural awareness

The utilize of the term "intercultural" reflects the see that learners of a remote dialect ought to pick up an understanding of both their claim social values and the outside culture. Intercultural communicative competence alludes to the capacity to supply a common understanding of individuals of diverse social characters and the capacity to bargain with complex numerous characters and their possess characters.

This competence emphasizes mediation between contrasts totally different societies, the capacity to see at oneself from an "exterior" point of see, to analyze and adjust one's behavior, values and convictions. Hence, the understudy illustrates a number of behavioral and cognitive capacities, to be specific:

- attitudes - recognition of the identity of others - respect and tolerance for others - empathy
 - behavior - flexibility - communicative awareness
 - cognitive abilities - knowledge - knowledge discovery - interpretation and translation - critical cultural consciousness
- By acquiring intercultural competence, learners realize relationships that allow them to interpret the values, beliefs and behavior of the "culture" of themselves and others and "stand on the bridge" or even "be a bridge" between representatives of different languages and cultures. Based on this concept, cultural learning is defined as the process of acquiring the required cultural knowledge, skills and abilities for effective communication and interaction with people from other cultures. It is a dynamic, evolving and ongoing process that engages learners in a cognitive, behavioral and emotional environment.

A energetic see of culture requires understudies to require an dynamic portion within the think about of culture, to consider social truths that are found in time and space, in districts, classes and eras. A energetic see of culture moreover requires learners to know their possess culture, the position of their possess social behaviors. On the premise of a certain hone and life encounter of individuals, a essential set of standards for acing the dialect and culture is proposed, specifically: 1) the ponder of societies by comparing them, 343 comparison and examination; 2) finding one's put "third put" between societies. This competence makes a difference them broaden their skylines and increment resistance. Social mindfulness covers three qualities:

- a) awareness of one's culturally induced behavior;
- b) awareness of the culturally induced behavior of others;
- c) the ability to explain one's cultural point of view.
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The following steps are suggested as a miniature model of the learning process:

1) Cultural exploration. Engaging learners in learning about their target culture through cultural research, such as:

- Ethnographic interview/research

Learners can conduct ethnographic interviews with native speakers invited to classes to interpret building their own cultural learning model through research on family values, for example. This type of activity is also possible outside the classroom - reading, listening, watching videos. The students are then asked to give an oral report on what they have learned about the target culture from their interviews/research. Ethnographic views are formed from various cognitive and behavioral outcomes of trainees. Ethnographic interviews shape attitudes towards speakers and the target culture, influencing the communication process.

1) Cultural simulations

Another exceptionally viable way to consider culture is to form social reenactments to study the target culture within the gathering of people. Understudies can be partitioned into little bunches to encourage socialization. Social modeling of any circumstance, both social and regular communication, and proficient is made. Today there's a large number of remote instructors within the republic. Utilizing this great opportunity, you'll organize a joint lunch or brunch, evening tea.

Dealing with cultural stereotypes Students participate in cultural research tasks to identify any cultural stereotypes. For example, they can present their ideas about the national cuisine of the target language through presentations, photos, videos, cooking. This task can help them think about the reputation of the national cuisine, encourage discussion of origins or borrowings.

Another stereotypical idea is about the family issue, for example, about living with parents before marriage in a Belarusian family and a family of the language being studied. Such research can contribute to heated discussions about the advantages and disadvantages of living with parents, which subsequently develop into disputes and debates. One should, however, be extremely careful when suggesting this kind of discussion and remember that many stereotypes do not take into account individuality and represent a negative judgment that can lead to misunderstanding. Many stereotypes represent prejudice, often having little to do with reality.

2) Comparing cultures

This step encourages students to look for cultural similarities and differences between the target culture and their own culture, based on an understanding of their own culture and based on their own acquired knowledge, beliefs and values. Group discussions and reflections are organized on cultural similarities and differences in family values between different cultures. For example, the model of the Belarusian family; priorities, values, differences between urban and rural life; men and women are equal in housework and childcare; parental authority; people over the age of 18 have the right to make their own decisions; new family patterns in Western European countries.

3) Intercultural mediation or third place This stage involves students in turning inward on cultural information through self-reflection and leads to an in-depth understanding of the role of culture/language in the worldview.

They draw conclusions, compare, interpret, discuss their role, their “third place”. In this process, learners worthy of their first culture observe the target culture and take the place of an intermediary where they can observe and reflect on both their own and the target cultural differences. This stage contributes to solving problems with cultural dilemmas. Participation in discussions should be encouraged and discussion of the results of the proposed solutions should be stimulated. For example, students may discuss dilemmas about career choices or dietary norms. Being in a mediating position, foreign language learners synthesize elements of different cultures and create their own understanding of cultural differences between these cultures. It is at this stage that the gap between cultural differences is overcome and the communicative goal is achieved.

In conclusion, it should be suggested that much of our possess social information is undetectable and connected in our day by day intelligent subliminally. It ought to be borne in intellect that an vital beginning point for learners may be a smooth move from their possess culture to the opportunity to effectively take an interest in comparing, differentiating and reflecting the social values of the target culture. The stages portrayed don't have a clear arrangement, and can be displayed simultaneously. The move from a conventional to an intercultural position within the classroom in a outside dialect can offer assistance both understudies and instructors in their proficient improvement and improvement. Intercultural competence will without a doubt be able to raise mindfulness of the inseparable and forbid relationship between dialect, culture and dialect learning would like to note that much of our own cultural knowledge is invisible and applied in our daily interactions subconsciously. It should be borne in mind that an important starting point for learners is a smooth transition from their own culture to the opportunity to actively participate in comparing, contrasting and reflecting the cultural values of the target culture. The stages described do not have a clear sequence, and can be presented simultaneously. The transition from a traditional to an intercultural position in the classroom in a foreign language can help both students and teachers in their professional development and development. Intercultural competence will undoubtedly be able to raise awareness of the inextricable and interdependent relationship between language, culture and language learning.

REFERENCES

1. Mitchell, R. Second language learning theories / R. Mitchell, F. Myles. – 2nd ed. - London : Hodder Arnold, 2004. - 374 p.
2. Dictionary of terms of intercultural communication [Electronic resource] / N. G. Zhukova. Access mode: <https://moodle.znu.edu.ua/pluginfile.php?file=/131433/mod>. – Access date: 11/24/2018.
3. Gall, J. P., Gall, M. D., & Borg, W. R. (2016). Applying educational research: A practical guide. P.156-160. New York: Longman.
4. Glesne, C. (2014-2018). Becoming qualitative researchers: An introduction. p.234-238. New York: Longman.
5. Grossman, P., Wineburg, S., & Beers, S. (2019). Introduction: When theory meets practice in the world of school. In S. Wineburg and P. Grossman (Eds.) Interdisciplinary curriculum: Challenges to implementation. p. 1-16., UK
6. New York: Teachers College Press. Hillison, J. (2016). Agriculture in the classroom: Early 1900s style. Journal of Agricultural Education, p. 11-18., UK
7. Doorenbos, A. Z., Schim, S. M., Benkert, R., & Borse, N. N. (2005). Psychometric evaluation of the cultural competence assessment instrument among healthcare providers. Nurs Res, 54(5), 324-331 p.